

[Mn(C₁₆N₂O₄H₁₁S)₂(CH₃OH)₄] : Facile synthesis of a new type of Mn complex formed by extensive π - π stacking interaction

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Abstract : The Mn^{II} complex, bis-(2-naphthol orange) tetra methanol manganese, [Mn(C₁₆N₂O₄H₁₁S)₂(CH₃OH)₄] (1) was synthesized by the reaction of Mn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O, NⁿBu₄MnO₄ and ZrO(NO₃)₂·9H₂O in a MeOH/MeCN solvent mixture. In this mononuclear complex the central Mn^{II} atom is coordinated to four methanol molecules and two 2-Naphthol Orange (2-npo) in an octahedral fashion. It has intermolecular π - π stacking and hydrogen bonding interactions leads to generate a 3-D metal-organic framework (MOF). The unit cell packing looks like one layer is stack to another. The π - π stacking and Mn...Mn distances are of 4.44 Å and 7.13 Å, respectively between the two closest layers. The cyclic-voltagram clearly indicates that manganese atoms are in +2 oxidation state that is further confirmed by BVS calculation. The nano molecular size of the complex is found to be 2.8 nm.

Keywords : Manganese complex, crystal structure, three-dimensional network, 2-npo, π - π stacking interactions.

Introduction

The synthesis and characterization of new heteropolynuclear manganese complexes have been of great interest over the last decades¹⁻³. Complexes of manganese have versatile properties like magnetism; photocatalytic due to its large number of unpaired electrons with respect to variable oxidation states. These are widely used in the field of bioinorganic chemistry (mainly photosynthesis)^{4,5} and single-molecule magnets^{6,7}. Crucial efforts in this field of work have led to the formation of high nuclearity species, which may be either homometallic or heterometallic. Christou *et al.* has synthesized top to bottom (Mn₈₄ to Mn₄) clusters with the help of carboxylate, oximes, triethanol

amine, azide etc.⁸. Though there is no such definite strategy to build high nuclearity metal clusters, but people have always tried to discovered different strategies to obtain higher nuclearity clusters⁹⁻¹¹. 2-Naphthol Orange has different donor sites i.e. N, O and S; those can easily coordinate metal atoms in different modes like pyrazoles, 2-pyridine oximes in different homo or heteromolecular clusters of Cu, Ni, Co etc.¹²⁻¹⁴. To our interest, on the other hand Zr metal containing compounds have been mainly used in different catalytic applications. But there are not many reports about the heteronuclear clusters containing both Mn and Zr metal atoms. Only few Mn-Zr systems are reported^{15,16}. Therefore our main objective is to

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synthesize new Mn-Zr clusters and study both biological activities as well as magnetic properties.

Herein, we report the synthesis and characterization of a new Mn^{II} complex with 2-Naphthol Orange (2-npo) ligand.

2-Naphthol Orange

Experimental

Syntheses : All manipulations were performed under aerobic conditions using chemicals and solvents as received.

Caution! Perchlorate salts and NⁿBu₄MnO₄ are potentially explosive, and such compounds should be synthesized and used in small quantities, and treated with utmost care at all times. The synthesis of NⁿBu₄MnO₄¹⁷ and 2-Naphthol Orange is reported elsewhere.

Synthesis and crystallization of C₃₆H₃₈N₄O₁₂S₂Mn (1) :

To a stirred solution of 2-Naphthol Orange (0.1 mmol, 0.035 g) and ZrO(NO₃)₂ (0.2 mmol, 0.046 g) was dissolved in 15 mL MeOH. Then Mn(ClO₄)₂ (0.5 mmol, 0.1810 g) was dissolved in 10 mL MeCN and added to it slowly with constant stirring in the previous mixture. Then NⁿBu₄MnO₄ (0.2 mmol, 0.0722 g) was added to it and the mixture was stirred for about another half an hour. The resulting dark brown slurry was filtered and the filtrate was kept in undisturbed condition in slow evaporation for crystallisation. After 3 days, high quality red coloured crystals came out and were washed with MeCN/MeOH (1 : 1, v/v) mixture. The yield was about 0.26 g (30%).

IR spectroscopy and elemental analysis :

The identity of the complex **1** was confirmed by IR spectroscopy and elemental analysis, which were

both in good agreement with the crystal structure analysis. Selected IR data (cm⁻¹) : 639 (w), 1035 (m), 1137 (m), 1384 (m), 1637 (m), 2938 (wk), 3456 (bs). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₆H₃₈MnN₄O₁₂S₂ (solvent-free) : C, 51.61; H, 4.57; N, 6.69. Found : C, 50.65; H, 4.31; N, 6.66%.

Single crystal X-ray diffraction :

Single crystal X-ray diffraction data of complex **1** was collected at 150 K on a Bruker SMART system equipped with an APEX II CCD area detector and a graphite monochromator utilizing Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å). An initial search for reciprocal space revealed monoclinic cell for **1**; space groups P2₁/c were confirmed by the subsequent solution and refinement of the structures. Cell parameters were refined using 21426 reflections. Raw data frames were read by the program SAINT¹⁸ and integrated using 3D profiling algorithms. The resulting data were reduced to produce *hkl* reflections and their intensities and estimated standard deviations. The data were corrected for Lorentz and polarization effects and numerical absorption corrections were applied based on indexed and measured faces. A full sphere of data (1850 frames) was collected using the ω -scan method (0.5° frame width). The first 50 frames were re-measured at the end of data collection to monitor instrument and crystal stability (maximum correction on I was < 1%). Absorption corrections by integration were applied on the basis of measured indexed crystal faces. The structures were solved by direct methods in SHELXTL6.1¹⁹ and refined on F2 using full-matrix least squares. The non-H atoms were treated anisotropically, whereas all of the H atoms were calculated in idealized positions and refined as riding on their respective C atoms. For complex **1**, the asymmetric unit consists of an only one Mn^{II} atom, two Naphthol Orange (npo) anions, and four methanol solvent molecules. Thus program SQUEEZE, a part of the PLATON²⁰ package of crystallographic software, was used to calculate the solvent disorder area and remove its contribution to the overall intensity data. In the final cycle of refinement, 21426 reflections (of which 13285 are observed with $I > 2\sigma(I)$)

were used to refine 1064 parameters and the resulting R1, wR2 and S (goodness of fit) were 5.14%, 12.08% and 0.899, respectively. The refinement was carried out by minimizing the wR2 function using F2 rather than F values. R1 is calculated to provide a reference to the conventional R value but its function is not minimized. Unit cell data and structure refinement details are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for complex **1**

Parameter	1
Formula	$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{38}\text{MnN}_4\text{O}_{12}\text{S}_2$
fw (g/mol)	837.76
Cryst syst.	monoclinic
Space group	$\text{P2}_1/\text{c}$
<i>a</i> (Å)	7.7446(8)
<i>b</i> (Å)	34.897(4)
<i>c</i> (Å)	7.1377(9)
α (deg)	90
β (deg)	105.963(7)
γ (deg)	90
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1854.67(4)
Z	2
T (K)	150(2)
Radiation (Å ^a)	0.71073
<i>r</i> (g/cm ³)	0.489
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.538
R1 ^{b,c}	0.0715
wR2 ^d	0.2056
CCDC No.	1517057

^aGraphite monochromator. ^b $I > 2\sigma(I)$. ^c $R1 = \Sigma(|F_o| - |F_c|) / \Sigma|F_o|$. ^d $wR2 = [\Sigma w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \Sigma[w(F_o^2)]^{1/2}$, $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (ap)^2 + bp]$, where $p = [F_o^2 + 2F_c^2]/3$.

Computer programs : APEX2 (Bruker, 2013), SAINT (Bruker, 2013), SHELXTL2013 (Bruker, 2013) and SHELXL2014 (Sheldrick, 2015).

Results and discussion

A variety of reaction systems involving different reagent ratios and solvent media was explored to develop the procedure described here. The reaction of 2-npo with $\text{ZrO}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Mn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $\text{N}^n\text{Bu}_4\text{MnO}_4$ in 1 : 2 : 5 : 2 ratio in MeOH/MeCN (15/10, v/v) gave a deep brown solution from which was subsequently isolated $[\text{Mn}(\text{C}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}_{11}\text{S})_2$ -

$(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_4]$ (**1**) in 30% yield. The reaction is summarized in eq. (1).

Using MeOH as the only solvent also leads to the same product, but the mixed-solvent system produced the crystalline product in highest yield. In absence of any of the reaction component i.e. $\text{Mn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{ZrO}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{N}^n\text{Bu}_4\text{MnO}_4$, does not lead to the product under similar condition.

The complex **1** crystallizes in monoclinic crystal system with $\text{P2}_1/\text{c}$ space group. The new asymmetric molecule possesses an unprecedented structure and partially labeled structure of complex **1** is represented in Fig. 1. Selected interatomic distances and angles are listed in Table 2. Fig. 1 indicates that Mn atom is hexa co-ordinated and it is surrounded by four methanol molecules and two anionic unit of 2-Naphthol Orange. Interestingly the +2 oxidation state of Mn atom in this complex is further confirmed by the BVS calculation of metal atoms (Table 3)^{21,22}.

All the oxygen atoms of the four methanol group (O5, O5' and O6, O6') and the oxygen atoms of 2-npo group (O3 and O3') are connected to the Mn atom in octahedral environment in the complex **1**. The ligand also appears as the O carrying single negative charge confirmed by the calculation of BVS of oxygen atoms (Table 4)^{23,24}. The different representation like ball and stick model, and space filling model of (**1**) are shown in Fig. 1. From the unit cell structure of complex **1** (Fig. 2), it is quite clear that the molecule exists in layer structure and it seems that the two layers are connected through O atom and extensive level of π - π stacking interactions between the two layers is present in the molecule. The π - π stacking, Mn...Mn distances and nanomolecular size of complex **1** is found to be 4.4 Å, 7.13 Å and 2.8 nm shown in Fig. 3. The most interesting feature of this molecule is the presence of both intra and intermolecular H-bonding. Intra and intermolecular H-bonding observed between (O1...H14; O2...H15) and

Fig. 1. (a) Partially labeled structure (top) and (b) octahedral space filling representation (bottom) of complex **1**. Color code : Mn^{II}, Deep green; O, Red; S, Yellow; N, Blue; C, Grey; H, light gray.

Table 2. Selected interatomic distances (Å) and angles (deg)^a for **1**

Metal	Atom	Bond length (Å)	Bond type	Angle (°)
Mn1	O3	2.126(5)	O3-Mn1-O6	0.77(19)
	O5	2.144(6)	O3-Mn1-O3	180
	O6	2.197(5)	O3-Mn1-O5	92.1(2)
	O3-S1	1.459(5)	O5-Mn1-O6	88.1(19)
	O4-C2	1.268(9)	O5-Mn1-O5	180
	O5-C18	1.385(12)	O6-Mn1-O6	180
	O6-C17	1.425(9)	O2-S1-O3	112.2(3)
			O2-S1-O1	114.2(3)
			O3-S1-O1	111.7(3)
			S1-O3-Mn1	147.4(4)

Table 3. Bond-valence sums^b for the metal atoms of complex^a

Complex	Atom	Mn ^{II}	Mn ^{III}	Mn ^{IV}
1	Mn1	<u>2.24</u>	2.06	2.02

^aThe oxidation state of a particular atom is the nearest integer to the underlined value. ^bThe underlined value is the closest to the charge for which it was calculated.

Table 4. Bond-valence sums^b for the O atoms of complex^a

Complex	Atom	BVS	Assignment	Group
1	O1/O1'	2.07	O ²⁻	O ²⁻
	O2/O2'	1.82	O ²⁻	O ²⁻
	O3/O3a	0.96	SO ₃ ⁻	SO ₃ ⁻
	O4/O4a	1.40	ROH	ROH
	O5/O5a	1.14	ROH	CH ₃ OH
	O6/O6a	1.02	ROH	CH ₃ OH

^aBVS values for O atoms of O²⁻, ROH, CH₃OH and SO₃⁻ groups are typically 1.8–2.0, 1.4, 1.0–1.4, and 0.9–1.0, respectively, but can be affected by hydrogen bonding.

(O1...H5; O2...H6A) and corresponding bond distances are found to be (2.79, 2.52) and (1.73, 2.07) Å, respectively (Figs. 4a and 4b). This type of interaction can also be represented as C-H...O type of interaction and it stabilizes the molecule. Fig. 4b also view the structure of the molecule looks like of helical type. The all H-bonding geometric parameters are enlisted in Table 5. The Mn-O3, Mn-O5 and Mn-O6

Fig. 2. Unit cell packing structure of complex **1**. Color code : Mn^{II}, Deep green; O, Red; S, Yellow; N, Blue; C, Grey; H, light grey.

Fig. 3. π - π stacking interaction of complex **1**.

bond distances are found to be 2.126(5), 2.144(6) and 2.197(5) Å, respectively.

From the UV-Vis absorption spectrum of the complex **1** (Fig. 5), observed one strong absorption peak at 478.404 nm originating from d-d transition may be $t_{2g} \rightarrow e_g$. In complex **1** Mn is in (II) oxidation state which is $3d^5$ octahedral systems and ground term is

${}^6A_{1g}$. Therefore the complex **1** behaves as low spin rather than $3d^5$ (high spin) electron systems which is laport and spins forbidden. The other two humps at 263 and 307 nm may be due to the presence of ligand centred transition in the complex. Fig. 6 represents the cyclic voltamogram for complex **1** and it shows irreversible process. The upper portion of this

Fig. 4a. Intramolecular H-bonding in complex 1 shown by dotted green bond.

Fig. 4b. Intermolecular H-bonding interactions of complex 1 shown by the dotted turquoise bond.

Table 5. Hydrogen bonding geometric parameters (Å and °) for complex 1

D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A
C14-H14...O1	0.9500	2.7900	3.423(9)	167.00
C15-H15...O2	0.9500	2.5200	2.900(9)	104.00

voltamogram indicates the reduction reaction of $Mn^{2+} + 2e = Mn$ and potential value is -1.0 and lower portion of the voltamogram supports the oxidation reaction of $Mn = Mn^{2+} + 2e$ and corresponding potential value is $+0.11$. The potential value of $+0.61$ and $+1.01$ V are not so prominent and it may be negligible. Therefore the system is predicted as Mn^{2+}/Mn and $E^0 = -1.11$ V²⁵.

Fig. 5. UV absorption spectrum for complex 1.

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammogram for complex 1.

Conclusions

In summary, we have successfully synthesized octahedral Mn^{II} complex employing 2-Naphthol Orange as ligand for the first time. The importance of the complex is in the fact that it has very uncommon π - π stacking interaction and stabilised by intra and intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions to give helical type of structure. Interestingly in absence of zirconium salt the complex 1 is not formed, may be it acts as a catalysts for formation of the complex. UV-Vis study of the complex 1 reveals that the existence of the d-d transition and the ligand centred transition in the complex. We are also synthesizing different hetero and homometallic cluster containing Mn and Zr. Hopefully these will be successful in the near future.

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Supporting Information

X-Ray crystallographic files in CIF format for (1), FTIR and ORTEP structure of (1).

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